

BUSINESS ANALYSIS OF MANUFACTURING OF SEED CLEANER BY PADSONS INDUSTRIES PVT. LTD., AKOLA

Saurabh Gopal Hande¹, Dr. N. T. Bagde² Dr. N. V. Shende³ Dr. Sangita Warade⁴1 Master of Business Administration in Agri-Business Management, School of Agri-Business Management, Nagpur.
saurabhhande173@gmail.com

2 Assistant Professor, Department of Agricultural Economics and Statistics, College of Agriculture, Nagpur.

3 Head Department of Agricultural Economics and Statistics, Dr. PDKV, Akola,

4 Professor (Agri-Business Management), School of Agri-Business Management, College of Agriculture under the jurisdiction of Dr. Panjabrao
Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth (Dr. PDKV), Nagpur, Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract

This research explores the business dynamics involved in the manufacturing of seed cleaner machines by Padsons Industries Pvt. Ltd., Akola, a reputed firm specializing in post-harvest agricultural machinery. Seed quality plays a vital role in agriculture as it directly impacts crop productivity, storage potential, and market value. Mechanized seed cleaners improve seed quality by effectively removing impurities such as dust, stones, and broken grains. The growing emphasis on agricultural mechanization, supported by various government schemes and the increased use of hybrid seeds, has boosted the demand for such machinery.

The main objectives of this study were to estimate the establishment cost of a seed cleaner manufacturing unit, assess the manufacturing costs of different seed cleaner models, and identify the primary challenges encountered in the manufacturing process. A descriptive research design was adopted, and primary data were collected through structured interviews with company officials, supervisors, and workers.

Findings indicate that seed cleaner manufacturing is a capital-intensive activity, with machinery and skilled labor forming major components of the cost structure. Variable costs, particularly raw materials and labor, contribute significantly to overall production expenses. The study also identified key constraints such as the requirement for high initial investment, scarcity of skilled labor, limited space in workshops, irregular raw material supply, and seasonal market demand. Despite these hurdles, Padsons Industries has maintained its competitive edge through a strong focus on innovation, quality assurance, and market responsiveness. The research offers useful insights for entrepreneurs, investors, and policymakers seeking to support agri-based rural enterprises and promote sustainable agricultural mechanization in India.

Keywords: manufacturing of seed cleaner, establishment cost, manufacturing costs, constraints

Introduction

Seed quality plays a critical role in Indian agriculture, directly impacting crop productivity and food security. Mechanized seed cleaner machines enhance seed purity by removing impurities like dust, stones, and broken grains, improving germination, yield, storage, and market value. Padsons Industries Pvt. Ltd., based in Akola and part of the Padgilwar Group, is a recognized manufacturer of high-performance post-harvest machinery, including seed cleaners tailored to Indian farming needs. With rising demand driven by government support, expanding hybrid seed use, and mechanization programs like SMAM and NFSM, the Indian seed processing machinery market is growing at 8–10% annually. This study focuses on the establishment cost of a unit, the manufacturing cost of

seed cleaner machines and constraints in the manufacturing of seed cleaners at Padsons, including cost structures. It highlights challenges such as raw material supply issues, skilled labor shortages, and seasonal market fluctuations, while also addressing opportunities in domestic and export markets. The study is valuable for entrepreneurs, policymakers, and stakeholders interested in rural industrialization, self-reliant manufacturing, and sustainable agriculture. Padsons' commitment to innovation, quality, and service is recognized through awards like the Best Industry Award and Udyogshree Award, positions it as a key player in advancing India's agricultural mechanization and supporting rural entrepreneurship.

Company Profile

Name of the Company	Padsons Industries Pvt. Ltd.
Factory Address	H-28/2, M.I.D.C. Phase III, Shioni, Akola – 444104 (MS)
Contact Persons	Mr. Shrikant Padgilwar – Managing Director Mr. Amit Shrikant Padgilwar – Director
Establishment	1999
Type of organization	Private Limited Company
Email Addresses	padsons@gmail.com
Type of Organization	Private Limited Company

Objectives

The objectives of the paper are given below
To work out establishment cost of selected unit.
To estimate manufacturing cost of seed cleaners.
To identify constraints in manufacturing of seed cleaners

Methodology:

The study titled “Business Analysis of Manufacturing of Seed Cleaner by Padsons Industries Pvt. Ltd., Akola” was conducted at the School of Agri-Business Management, Nagpur during the 2024–25 academic session. The research aimed to assess establishment and production costs, break-even analysis, marketing practices, and production challenges. A descriptive research design was used, incorporating primary data. Primary data was collected through interviews and structured

questionnaires with company personnel.

Source of data**Primary Data**

The primary data were collected by a pretested schedule from concerned officials, supervisors, skilled labours etc. of the selected firm by personal interview method regarding the establishment cost, manufacturing cost, marketing, etc.

Period of the data

The present study was based on primary data. The data was collected for the period of the financial year 2024-25

Analytical Tools:

The selection of statistical and analytical tools was based on the study's objectives and the type of data collected. The methods used for analysis

in this study are explained below

Establishment cost of selected unit

The fixed capital on buildings, machinery, land, and furniture was collected and presented by simple tabular analysis in results

Manufacturing cost of seed cleaner

The collected data was analysed, tabulated on the following different aspects.

Fixed Cost:

The fixed cost includes the data regarding the cost of machinery, building, land, furniture, salary of staff, electricity charges, insurance premium, taxes, etc. collected from a selected firm.

Variable Cost

The variable cost consists of expenditure on the purchase of raw material,

wages of casual labour, oil and lubricants, repair and maintenance of machinery, etc.

Total Cost

The total cost of processing comprised of the total fixed cost, total variable cost was calculated by adding these costs together

Constraints in the manufacturing of the seed cleaner

The simple tabular analysis was carried out to identify the constraints in the manufacturing of seed cleaners of the selected unit

Results and Discussion

This study analyzes the business aspects of seed cleaner manufacturing at Padsons Industries Pvt. Ltd., Akola, focusing on setup, production, marketing, and financial operations. Key data was collected and examined to meet the project objectives, with findings presented in a structured manner.

Table 1: Establishment cost of selected unit

Sr.No	Items	Amount(Rs)	Percentage
1	Land	7000000	21.24
2	construction	8000000	24.28
3	Machinery	17025400	51.67
4	Furniture and Fixtures, and Appliances	334400	1.01
5	Permanent Labour	540000	1.64
6	Licence Fees	50000	0.15
	Total	32949800	100

As shown in table 1, the total capital investment required for setting up the selected unit amounts to ₹3.29 crores. The largest portion of this investment, 51.67%, is allocated to machinery, reflecting the capital-intensive nature of the manufacturing process. This is followed by expenditure on construction (24.28%) and land acquisition (21.24%), which together make up a significant 45.52% of the total investment.

Smaller allocations include furniture, fixtures, and appliances at 1.01%, permanent labour costs at 1.64%, and license fees at 0.15%. Each of these components plays a crucial role in establishing a fully functional and legally compliant manufacturing unit

Table 2: Fixed cost for manufacturing Destoner seed cleaner

Sr No	Cost Component	per unit cost in Rs	Annual cost in Rs (60 Machine)	percentage
1	Depreciation of building@5%	3653.85	219230.77	24.06
2	Depreciation of machine@10%	6950.16	417009.46	45.77
3	Depreciation of Furniture, Fixture@10% and Appliances@15%	426.90	25614.00	2.81
4	per annum salary of permanent labour	4153.85	249230.77	27.36
	Total	15184.75	911085.00	100.00

The above table 2 outlines the annual fixed cost of ₹9,11,085 for producing 60 seed cleaner machines. The largest share is machinery depreciation at ₹4,17,009.46 (45.77%), followed by permanent labour salaries at ₹2,49,230.77 (27.36%), and building depreciation at

₹2,19,230.77 (24.06%). Minor costs include depreciation on furniture and appliances at ₹25,614 (2.81%). The fixed cost per unit comes to ₹15,184.75, highlighting the capital-intensive nature of the business, driven mainly by machinery and skilled labour.

Table 3: Fixed cost for manufacturing Gravity seed cleaner

Sr No	Cost Component	Per unit cost in Rs	Annual cost in Rs(40 Machine)	percentage
1	Depreciation of building@5%	3653.85	146153.85	24.06
2	Depreciation of machine@10%	6950.16	278006.31	45.77
3	Depreciation of Furniture, Fixture @10%and Appliances@15%	426.90	17076.00	2.81
4	Per annum salary of permanent labour	4153.85	166153.85	27.36
	Total	15184.75	607390.00	100.00

The above table 3 shows the fixed cost structure for producing 40 Gravity Seed Cleaners, totaling ₹6,07,390 annually. The highest cost share is machinery depreciation (₹2,78,006.31; 45.77%), followed by permanent labour salaries (₹1,66,153.85; 27.36%) and building depreciation

(₹1,46,153.85; 24.06%). Depreciation on furniture and appliances contributes the least (₹17,076; 2.81%). The fixed cost per unit is ₹15,184.75, indicating that capital assets and labour are the main cost drivers.

Table 4: Fixed cost for manufacturing Grader seed cleaner

Sr No	Cost Component	Per unit cost in Rs	Annual cost in Rs (30 Machine)	percentage
1	Depreciation of building@5%	3653.85	109615.38	24.06

2	Depreciation of machine@10%	6950.16	208504.73	45.77
3	Depreciation of Furniture, Fixture @10%and Appliances@15%	426.90	12807.00	2.81
4	Per annum salary of permanent labour	4153.85	124615.38	27.36
	Total	15184.75	455542.50	100

The above table 4 presents the fixed cost structure for producing 30 Grader Seed Cleaners, totaling ₹4,55,542.50 annually. The highest cost is machinery depreciation at ₹2,08,504.73 (45.77%), followed by permanent labour salaries at ₹1,24,615.38 (27.36%) and building

depreciation at ₹1,09,615.38 (24.06%). Minor depreciation on furniture and appliances is ₹12,807 (2.81%). The fixed cost per unit is ₹15,184.75, highlighting machinery and labour as the main cost contributors.

Table 5: Variable cost for manufacturing Destoner seed cleaner

Sr No	Cost Component	Per unit Cost	Annual cost in Rs (60 Machine)	percentage
1	Raw material	39667	2380020	74.47
2	Labour cost	6000	360000	11.26
3	Electricity Cost	2000	120000	3.75
4	Assembly charges	600	36000	1.13
5	Consumables (welding rods, lubricants)	800	48000	1.50
6	Tools wear And Tear (drill bits, cutting blades)	200	12000	0.38
7	colouring and polishing	4000	240000	7.51
8	Total	53267	3196020	100.00

The above table 5 outlines the variable cost structure for producing 60 Destoner Seed Cleaners, totaling ₹31,96,020 annually. Raw materials are the major component at ₹23,80,020 (74.47%), followed by labour at ₹3,60,000 (11.26%) and colouring, polishing at ₹2,40,000 (7.51%).

Electricity costs ₹1,20,000 (3.75%), with smaller expenses from consumables (₹48,000), assembly (₹36,000), and tool wear (₹12,000). The per unit variable cost is ₹53,267, highlighting raw materials and labour as the primary cost drivers

Table 6: Variable cost for manufacturing Gravity seed cleaner

Sr No	Cost Component	Per unit cost	Annual cost in Rs(40machine)	percentage
1	Raw material	56464	2258560	71.33
2	Labour cost	12000	480000	15.16
3	Electricity Cost	2500	100000	3.16
4	Assembly charges	2400	96000	3.03
5	Consumables (welding rods, lubricants)	1000	40000	1.26
6	Tools wear And Tear (drill bits, cutting blades)	300	12000	0.38
7	Colouring and polishing	4500	180000	5.68
8	Total	79164	3166560	100.00

The above table 6 details the variable cost for producing 40 Gravity Seed Cleaners, totaling ₹31,66,560 annually. Raw materials are the largest component at ₹22,58,560 (71.33%), followed by labour at ₹4,80,000 (15.16%) and colouring/polishing at ₹1,80,000 (5.68%). Electricity

(₹1,00,000), assembly (₹96,000), consumables (₹40,000), and tool wear (₹12,000) make up the rest. The per unit variable cost is ₹79,164, with raw materials and labour as the primary cost contributors

Table 7: Variable cost for manufacturing Grader seed cleaner

Sr No	Cost Component	Per unit cost	Annual cost in Rs(30 machine)	percentage
1	Raw material	66414	1992420	78.21
2	Labour cost	9000	270000	10.60
3	Electricity Cost	2000	60000	2.36
4	Assembly charges	1800	54000	2.12
5	consumables(welding rods, lubricants)	1000	30000	1.18
6	Tools wear And Tear (drill bits, cutting blades)	200	6000	0.24
7	colouring and polishing	4500	135000	5.30
8	Total	84914	2547420	100

The above table 7 shows the variable cost for producing 30 Grader Seed Cleaners, totaling ₹25,47,420 annually. Raw materials are the largest cost at ₹19,92,420 (78.21%), followed by labour at ₹2,70,000 (10.60%) and colourin polishing at ₹1,35,000 (5.30%). Other costs include electricity

(₹60,000), assembly (₹54,000), consumables (₹30,000), and tool wear (₹6,000). The per unit variable cost is ₹84,914, with raw materials and labour being the major cost contributors

Table 8: Total cost for manufacturing Destoner seed cleaner

Sr. No	Particulars	Per unit cost	Annual cost in Rs (60 Machine)	Percentage
1	Fixed cost	15184.75	911085.00	22.18
2	Variable cost	53267.00	3196020.00	77.82
	Total cost	68451.75	4107105.00	100

The above table 8 summarizes the total cost for producing 60 Destoner Seed Cleaners, amounting to ₹41,07,105 annually, with a per unit cost of ₹68,451.75. Variable costs dominate at ₹31,96,020 (77.82%), driven by materials, labour, and utilities. Fixed costs total ₹9,11,085 (22.18%),

covering depreciation and salaries. The data highlights that variable costs are the main expense, emphasizing the need for efficient material use and production processes.

Table 9: Total cost for manufacturing Gravity seed cleaner

Sr. No	Particulars	Per unit cost	Annual cost in Rs (40 machine)	Percentage
1	Fixed cost	15184.75	607390.00	16.09
2	Variable cost	79164.00	3166560.00	83.91
	Total cost	94348.75	3773950.00	100.00

The above table 9 shows the total cost for producing 40 Gravity Seed Cleaners at ₹37,73,950 annually, with a per unit cost of ₹94,348.75. Variable costs dominate at ₹31,66,560 (83.91%), mainly from raw

materials and labour. Fixed costs are ₹6,07,390 (16.09%), covering depreciation and salaries. The data highlights the importance of managing variable costs to enhance production efficiency.

Table 10: Total cost for manufacturing Grader seed cleaner

Sr. No	Particulars	Per unit cost	Annual cost in Rs(30 Machine)	Percentage
1	Fixed cost	15184.80	455542.50	15.17
2	Variable cost	84914.00	2547420.00	84.83
	Total cost	100098.80	3002962.50	100.00

The above table 10 presents the cost structure for manufacturing 30 units of the Grader Seed Cleaner, with a total annual cost of ₹30,02,962.50 and a per unit cost of ₹1,00,098.80. Variable costs dominate at 84.83% (₹25,47,420), driven by raw materials, labour, and operations. Fixed

costs contribute 15.17% (₹4,55,542.50), covering depreciation and permanent staff salaries. The high share of variable costs highlights the importance of input efficiency and process optimization for improved profitability

Table 11: constraints in the manufacturing of seed cleaner

Sr. No.	constraints	Rank
1	High initial investment	I
2	Limited demand in a certain market	V
3	lack of Skilled labour	II
4	Limited Workshop Area	IV
5	Inconsistent raw material supply	III
6	Need time to time maintenance of the machine	VI
7	Human error in handling of the machine	VII
8	Safety of labour during the handling of the machine	VIII

The above table 11 shows the Manufacturing seed cleaner machines faces several constraints, including high initial investment, seasonal and regional demand, and skilled labor shortages. Small workshops with limited space hinder workflow, while inconsistent raw material supply affects production quality. Frequent maintenance needs and human errors increase after-sales issues, and worker safety is often neglected due to inadequate equipment and training.

Conclusion

This study investigates the business aspects of seed cleaner manufacturing at Padsons Industries Pvt. Ltd., Akola, a recognized producer of post-harvest agricultural machinery. Seed quality is vital for agricultural productivity, and mechanized seed cleaners play a crucial role by removing impurities like dust, stones, and broken grains.

The total establishment cost of the unit was estimated at ₹3.29 crores, with machinery contributing the highest share at 51.67%, indicating the capital-intensive nature of the operation. Manufacturing costs were assessed for three seed cleaner models: Destoner, Gravity, and Grader. The per unit costs were ₹68,451.75, ₹94,348.75, and ₹1,00,098.80, respectively, with variable costs accounting for over 75% of total costs in each case, primarily due to raw materials and labor.

The study identified major constraints such as high initial investment, shortage of skilled labor, limited workshop space, and inconsistent raw material supply. Despite these issues, Padsons Industries remains

competitive through its commitment to innovation, quality, and market expansion.

This research provides actionable insights for entrepreneurs, manufacturers, and policymakers involved in promoting rural industrialization and agricultural mechanization.

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